

Numerical modelling of shear cutting in complex phase high strength steel sheets: A comprehensive study using the Particle Finite Element Method

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the shear cutting process of Advanced High Strength Steel using the Particle Finite Element Method. Shear cutting, a crucial process in sheet metal forming, often leads to microcracks and plastic deformation that degrades the material performance in subsequent applications, such as cold forming, crashworthiness, and fatigue resistance. This work utilises the Particle Finite Element Method as an alternative to conventional Finite Element Methods to address the challenges of large deformation solid mechanics, offering high predictive accuracy in localised shearing deformation and fracture. The model was validated against experimental data from sheet punching tests, with evaluations at both macroscopic and mesoscopic levels, including cut edge profiles and microstructural deformation within the shear-affected zone. The Particle Finite Element Method approach demonstrated a high level of accuracy in predicting cut edge shape and shear-induced damage across various cutting conditions. As an unconventional numerical technique, usage of the Particle Finite Element Method advances modelling of large deformations solid mechanics and providing a robust tool for optimising manufacturing processes of materials sensitive to sheared edge damage.

1. Introduction

Shear cutting is a fundamental cutting technique in the sheet metal forming process, due to cost-efficiency, preciseness and automation possibilities. The shear cutting process often precedes cold-forming of sheet metal parts in i.e. the automotive sector for manufacturing of structural- and safety components. However, for high strength sheet materials, such as advanced high strength steel (AHSS) and high strength aluminium, the cutting process may introduce damage to the cut edge consisting of microcracks, severe plastic deformation and large geometrical notches [1]. The sheared edge damage is known to negatively effect the post-cutting performance of AHSS, manifested by reduced formability through edge cracking [2–4] and a decline in fatigue life [5,6]. Additionally, the sheared edge damage imposed by the shear cutting process can accelerate hydrogen embrittlement [7,8].

The effect of the sheared edge damage on sheet formability and part properties may vary depending on the shape of the final cut edge and the deformation imposed on its shear affected zone (SAZ). The shape of the cut edge, i.e. the *cut edge morphology*, is

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Fig. 1. Schematic images of the characteristic shear cutting processes (a) rollover, (b) shearing, (c) fracture and (d) the final cut edge morphology displaying the cut edge parameters.

to the greatest extent controlled by process parameters such as cutting clearance, cutting speed, tool shape and tool edges, where the cutting clearance and cutting speed are the most influential. The cutting clearance is defined by the distance between the punch and the die, as declared in Fig. 1, which schematically shows the shear cutting process. During the three stages of the shear cutting process, shown in Fig. 1(a) to (c), the rollover, the burnish surface, the fracture surface are created and sometimes a burr is formed. The height of these geometrical features define the four main cut edge parameters, as shown in Fig. 1(d). Depending on the above mentioned processing the distribution of these four cut edge parameters may vary.

By the use of numerical modelling, process response and sheared edge damage can be predicted in shear cutting simulations. Such modelling may be applied for cutting tool design, avoiding costly manufacturing stops in early product development. Most of the published shear cutting models use the Finite Element Method (FEM) for solving the governing equations. Due to the extreme deformation occurring in the shearing process, these FE-models require re-meshing schemes in order to avoid numerical issues related to distorted elements. Such model were published by Thipprakmas et al. [9] and Canales et al. [10] among others, modelling shear cutting for process optimisation purposes. In addition, use of arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation (ALE) enables the material to move independently to the mesh, providing a complementary solution to the element distortion issue if used in combination with re-meshing algorithms. In publications by Zhao et al. [11] and Gutknecht et al. [12], this modelling approach was proven useful when predicting the residual results of sheared edges of AHSS. Similarly, Pätzold et al. [13] used it for two-stage shear cutting. However, both Gutknecht et al. [12] and Cremonesi et al. [14] declare that extensive use of re-meshing might cause results smoothing, while ALE can be limited in defining unpredictable deformation and separation of material as in the case of material fracture.

With the modelling implications in mind, the present work proposes the use of the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) as an alternative numerical method for shear cutting simulations. PFEM is a Lagrangian particle method developed by Idelsohn et al. [15] proven to be suitable for large deformation solid mechanics where creation of new surfaces are present. It was first intended for solving fluid dynamics problems and uses the interpolation functions of FEM for particle interaction. The PFEM scheme utilises

Table 1

Tensile properties in different material directions relative to the rolling direction (RD) for CP1000HD with a thickness of $t = 1.5$ mm, yield strength (YS), tensile strength (UTS), uniform elongation (UE), total elongation ($A80$), n -value at uniform elongation (nAg) and r -value determined at 4% elongation ($r4$).

RD	YS [MPa]	UTS [MPa]	UE [%]	$A80$ [%]	nAg [-]	$r4$ [-]
0°	893	1052	7.3	11.1	0.071	0.91
45°	905	1052	7.0	10.6	0.068	1.02
90°	909	1062	7.1	10.7	0.068	0.96

continuous particle re-connectivity in order to avoid distorted elements. Delaunay triangulation is applied in the re-connectivity steps for ensuring good element aspect ratios. The Lagrangian formulation of PFEM and the re-connectivity strategy also makes it suitable for large deformation solid mechanics. For instance, Oñate et al. [16] showcased the use of PFEM for industrial forming processes of metals, such as forging and cutting. The latter has also been thoroughly addressed by Rodríguez et al. [17] for orthogonal cutting of metals. In the present work, PFEM is applied for numerical modelling of shear cutting and the model used extends from the publication by Sandin et al. [18], that presented the development of an axisymmetric PFEM model and the implementation of ductile damage- and failure capabilities in the PFEM scheme. The PFEM shear cutting strategy adopts the re-connectivity scheme presented by Rodríguez et al. [19] which was proven to minimise results diffusion and smoothing. By adding ductile damage- and failure modelling to the PFEM framework, Sandin et al. [18] extended the use of PFEM to shear cutting applications, which to large extent is controlled by crack initiation and fracture. This contrasts with the metal cutting processes traditionally modelled using PFEM, such as orthogonal cutting, which focus on plane strain material flow around the tool tip rather than accounting for material failure during surface generation in axisymmetric conditions. The PFEM shear cutting model could with good accuracy predict hole punching processes and showed robust treatment of time step size and mesh size dependency for the ductile damage and failure model. The near-isotropic behaviour of the AHSS grade investigated allowed for the use of an axisymmetric formulation, enabling efficient and fast simulations.

The main objective of this study is to thoroughly validate the PFEM methodology developed by Sandin et al. [18] for sheet punching operations. Validation is conducted on multiple levels. First, macroscopic cut edge parameters such as rollover, burnish, fracture, burr, and punching load are examined over an unprecedented range of cutting clearances. Next, cut edge profiles and geometric notches are compared with simulation results for a more detailed analysis. Finally, on a mesoscopic scale, the characteristics of the shear-affected zone near the cut edge are examined by analysing microstructural grain rotation in etched metallographic cross-sections and comparing it to numerical material rotation. This analysis introduces a novel validation technique that directly compares observed grain angles with numerical material rotation to evaluate sheared edge deformation, providing an alternative to approaches that translate grain rotation into equivalent strain [1,20] or relate experimental Vickers hardness measurements to SAZ strain [20,21]. The publication by Sandin et al. [18] focused on developing a PFEM framework with ductile damage modelling capabilities. In contrast, the current work broadens the scope of the PFEM shear cutting technique by exploring an unparallelled range of cutting parameters and incorporating extensive validation. This approach provides deeper insights into the shear deformation behaviour of AHSS, with practical implications for the properties of subsequent behaviour of the sheared edge. The PFEM model presented offers high predictive accuracy with low computational cost, making it a valuable asset for material and process development aimed at enhancing AHSS sheet manufacturing. Furthermore, employing a non-conventional numerical formulation for modelling the shear cutting process could expand the understanding of how large deformation solid mechanics problems can be addressed, thereby contributing to advancements in the field of computational mechanics.

2. Experimental methods

In this study, the 1.5 mm CR700Y980T-CH automotive sheet steel was examined in its cold-rolled, pickled, and continuously annealed condition. Hereafter, this grade will be referred to as CP1000HD. CP1000HD is a complex phase steel characterised by high ductility and an ultimate tensile strength of 1000 MPa. It is widely used in automotive applications, particularly in crash management systems and structural components. The microstructure of CP1000HD consists of fine-grained, homogeneous bainite, martensite, and retained austenite. The tensile properties of the material according to ISO 6892-1 [22] tensile test are provided in Table 1.

2.1. Sheet punching experiment and cut edge examination

Sheet punching experiments according to the ISO 16630 standard [23] were applied in the present work for validation of the PFEM shear cutting modelling. Sheet punching is a shear cutting process widely utilised in the sheet forming industry, particularly prior to hole collaring operations. The process involves producing a hole in the sheet by applying a fixed die and a moving punch, as illustrated schematically in Fig. 1.

A critical parameter in the hole punching process is the cutting clearance, which refers to the horizontal distance between the punch and the die. This clearance is typically expressed as a percentage, calculated using Eq. (1), where R_{Die} and R_{Punch} represent the radii of the die and punch, respectively, and t_B denotes the thickness of the blank

$$\text{Clearance [\%]} = \frac{R_{Die} - R_{Punch}}{t_B} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Table 2

The geometric hole punching parameters used in experiments for clearances (Cl.) 5.3–40.3%, where D_D is the die diameter, D_p is the punch diameter, $R_{D,e}$ is the die edge radius, $R_{p,e}$ is the punch edge radius and t_B is the blank thickness.

Cl. [%]	5.3	8.5	10.5	12.1	17.1	20.5	23.8	27.0	33.7	40.3
D_D [mm]	10.16	10.25	10.31	10.36	10.51	10.61	10.71	10.81	11.01	11.21
D_p [mm]						9.998				
$R_{D,e}$ [μm]						30				
$R_{p,e}$ [μm]						30				
t_B [mm]						1.5				

Fig. 2. Definition of the fracture angles.

Punching experiments were performed using cutting clearances ranging from 5.3% to 40.3%, employing a servo-hydraulic machine with a maximum load capacity of 150 kN. To the authors’ knowledge this work explores the effect of cutting clearance through testing a lot of different clearance values from a short values (5.3%) to a large one (40.3%). Cutting clearance in typical sheet shearing applications lies between 10 and 15%. Out of this range values were included to test the robustness of the proposed numerical approach. The press cylinder force was measured using a calibrated 200 kN strain gauge, while punch displacement was recorded with a 100 mm LVDT sensor. A blank holder spring force of 5 to 15 kN was applied before the punching operation. In accordance with the ISO 16630 standard, the piston speed was set to 0.05 mm/s to ensure quasi-static loading, minimising the influence of strain-rate hardening and adiabatic effects. While these low cutting speeds differ from typical industrial high-speed cutting, the standard provides controlled conditions that reduce strain-rate and thermal impacts, allowing for a clear assessment of material behaviour and ensuring reproducible results. As declared in the ISO 16630 standard, a 10 mm hole was punched at the centre of a 100 × 100 mm sheet using a four-column tool, ensuring tight coaxiality and clearance precision ($\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$). Both the punch and die, made from Vanadis 8/10 tool steel with a titanium carbonitride coating, featured sharp cutting edges with an estimated 30 μm radius. All geometric cutting parameters are listed in Table 2.

The experimental cut edges were examined using two non-destructive, high-resolution optical testing methods. Panoramic 2D imaging with EISYS [24] provided digitised distribution data of cut edge parameters along the perimeter, enabling quantitative comparison between experimental and numerical cut edges. Through the use of a Keyence stereo 3D microscope (VHX-7000), experimental cut edge profiles were extracted at arbitrary positions around the hole perimeter for direct comparison between the experimental and numerical cut edge shapes. The cut edge profiles were obtained by an innovative mirror technique that allowed 3D microscopy at the top-, front- and bottom areas of the cut edge, where stitching of the three images created the full cut edge profile. With the experimental cut edge profiles, the fracture angles were measured at positions located at 0°, 90°, 180° and 270° around the hole circumference for each cutting clearance. In this work, the fracture angle was determined between a best fit tangential line in fracture zone and the vertical burnish surface axis. Fig. 2 shows how the fracture angle β was defined for both (a) no-burr and (b) burr conditions, whereas (c) shows the two fracture angles β_1 and β_2 associated with secondary burnish formation.

Additionally, metallographic cut edge cross sections produced by etching enabled grain rotation measurements in the bulk material, enabling in depth assessment of the SAZ. With the grain rotation technique, the width and level of deformation imposed by the shear cutting process was possible to define in a close-cut configuration.

Interrupted hole punching experiments were conducted in order to step-wise investigate the formation of the sheared edge. These experiments were performed using an electromechanical Instron 5900R tensile machine mounted with a column guided punching tool. This experimental setup provided precise force versus punch displacement output, thus exact displacement levels

Table 3

The geometric hole punching parameters used in interrupted punching experiments, where D_D is the die diameter, D_p is the punch diameter, $R_{D,e}$ is the die edge radius, $R_{p,e}$ is the punch edge radius and t_B is the blank thickness.

Cl. [%]	D_D [mm]	D_p [mm]	$R_{D,e}$ [μ m]	$R_{p,e}$ [μ m]	t_B [mm]
9.0	10.27	10.00	30	30	1.5
Test nr.	Punch disp. [mm]				
1	0.73				
2	0.76				
3	0.78				
4	0.80				

at interruption. For each interruption, the specimen was cut at 0° and 90° to rolling direction and the cut edges were examined with a Scanning Electrode Microscope (SEM). Interrupted tests were time consuming so the detailed study about crack initiation was directed only to one cutting clearance. The results will serve to validate the modelling approach from a phenomenological point of view. The process parameters and punch displacement levels for the interrupted punching experiments are shown in Table 3.

3. Numerical modelling

Numerical sheet punching models were developed based on the work by Sandin et al. [18], utilising PFEM for axisymmetrical modelling of the shear cutting process. This section briefly explains PFEM and gives a description of the numerical modelling developed for modelling of the sheet punching cases in Table 2

3.1. The particle finite element method

PFEM is a particle method developed by Idelsohn et al. [15], intended for solving fluid dynamic problems in a Lagrangian manner and applies FE interpolation for defining particle interaction. The PFEM scheme performs continuous particle re-connectivity during the simulation to avoid distorted elements, enabling PFEM to model large material deformation without impairing the numerical accuracy, otherwise associated with overly deformed elements. Additionally, the use of a FE-framework for solving the governing equations gives the PFEM scheme a low computational cost compared to other particle methods such as smooth particle hydrodynamics or smoothed particle Galerkin. Depending on the problem at hand, the governing equations solved by the PFEM scheme may vary, but the essential PFEM procedure, as stated by Oriate et al. [25], is as follows:

1. Define a domain with particles and discretise the domain with a FE-mesh using the particles as the element nodes.
2. The so-called α -shape method defines internal and external boundaries.
3. Solve the governing equations.
4. Based on the solution of step 3, move the particles to their updated positions.
5. Perform particle re-connectivity continuously using Delaunay triangulation to avoid excessive element deformation.
6. Repeat from step 2.

In the proposed shear cutting scheme for solid PFEM modelling, the standard PFEM steps are slightly modified. Specifically, the α -shape method traditionally employed for boundary definition is replaced with constrained Delaunay triangulation described by Shewchuk [26]. This modification constrains the external boundaries of the blank domain, eliminating the need to use the α -shape method to remove excessively distorted elements at the boundaries formed by the Delaunay triangulation. Additionally, constrained Delaunay triangulation allows for different element sizes along the boundaries and supports volume conservation in PFEM, addressing a known challenge of the method discussed in detail by Franci and Cremonesi [27]. Another alteration of the conventional PFEM scheme consists of the results variable transfer. The results stored in the particles, such as displacement and pressure, are directly transferred to the new configuration during the particle re-connectivity step (step 5), as the particle distribution typically remains unchanged. However, the presented PFEM shear cutting model also stores historical results variables at the Gauss points of the elements, which must be transferred to the updated configuration. To minimise excessive smoothing and diffusion of results during this process, the current PFEM implementation employs the strategy proposed by Rodríguez et al. [19,28], where Gauss point values are transferred directly to the new mesh using a closest point projection.

3.2. Governing equations and problem solution

The governing equations for the shear cutting problem establishing a stabilised mixed finite element formulation from the momentum balance equation for the blank material, as expressed in Eq. (2), and from the pressure term p in Eq. (3), originating from the Cauchy stress tensor σ_{ij} .

$$\rho a_i - \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} - \rho b_i = 0 \quad \text{in } V \times [0, T]. \quad (2)$$

$$p = \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\sigma_{ij}). \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (2), the blank material domain is defined by V over the time interval $[0, T]$ with tensor notation of indices $i, j = 1, 2, 3$, ρ is the material density, a_i denotes acceleration and ρb_i accounts for external body forces.

The pressure term p was reformulated based on the approach outlined by Simo and Hughes [29], linking it to the hyperelastic potential, as expressed in Eq. (4). In this formulation, κ is the material compressibility modulus, and J is the Jacobian determinant:

$$p - \kappa \frac{\ln(J)}{J} = 0 \quad \text{in } V \times [0, T]. \quad (4)$$

The weak form of the momentum balance equation (Eq. (2)) is derived by multiplying it with a test function δu_i , integrating over the domain, and applying the divergence theorem, as described by Bonet et al. [30]. This yields Eq. (5):

$$\int_V \delta u_i \rho a_i dV + \int_V \varepsilon_{ij} \sigma_{ij} dV - \int_V \delta u_i \rho b_i dV - \int_S \delta u_i t_i dS = 0. \quad (5)$$

In the above, t_i denotes the traction forces per unit area on the boundary, S represents the boundary surface, and $\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \delta u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \delta u_j}{\partial x_i} \right)$ is the strain tensor.

Similarly, the weak form of the pressure equation (Eq. (4)) was derived by multiplying it with a test function δp and integrating over the volume V , leading to Eq. (6):

$$\int_V \delta p \frac{\ln(J)}{J} dV - \int_V \delta p \frac{p}{\kappa} dV = 0. \quad (6)$$

For axisymmetric cases, the differential volume dV is expressed as $dV = 2\pi r dA$, where r is the radial position of a discrete point, and dA is the differential area.

The PFEM implementation in the current work utilised axisymmetric triangular elements where the mixed pressure–displacement formulation prevented volumetric locking of elements in near-incompressibility J2-plasticity. For the numerical solution of the problem, the governing equations were discretised into finite element form, where the nodal displacements \mathbf{u} and pressures \mathbf{p} are interpolated as in Eqs. (7a) and (7b), where, \mathbf{N}_u and \mathbf{N} are the shape functions.

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{N}_u \bar{\mathbf{u}}, \quad (7a)$$

$$\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{N} \bar{\mathbf{p}}. \quad (7b)$$

Applying these discretisation to the weak forms of the governing equations (Eqs. (5) and (6)) yielded the residual equations presented in Eq. (8a) for the displacement residual \mathbf{R}_u and (8b) for the pressure related residual \mathbf{R}_p . Here, \mathbf{M}_u and the \mathbf{M}_p denotes the mass matrices associated with the displacement and pressure field, while $\mathbf{f}_{u,\text{ext}}$ are the external forces, $\mathbf{P}_u(\bar{\mathbf{u}})$ are the internal forces, $\mathbf{f}_{p,\text{stab}}(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$ is a stabilisation term for the pressure and $\mathbf{F}_{p,\text{vol}}$ are the volumetric forces. The terms $\bar{\mathbf{a}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{p}}$ are the accelerations, displacements and pressure respectively. The residuals are calculated for the updated time step $n+1$. The matrices forming the system of equations in Eqs. (8a) and (8b) are detailed in Appendix A.

$$\mathbf{R}_u = \mathbf{M}_u^{n+1} \bar{\mathbf{a}}^{n+1} - \mathbf{f}_{u,\text{ext}}^{n+1} + \mathbf{P}_u^{n+1}(\bar{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1}) = 0, \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_p = \mathbf{M}_p \bar{\mathbf{p}}^{n+1} + \mathbf{f}_{p,\text{stab}}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}^{n+1}) - \mathbf{F}_{p,\text{vol}}(\bar{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1}) = 0. \quad (8b)$$

The nodal accelerations in the residual equations $\bar{\mathbf{a}}^{n+1}$ were determined using the trapezoidal rule as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{v}}^{n+1} = \bar{\mathbf{v}}^n + \frac{2}{h} (\bar{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1} - \bar{\mathbf{u}}^n), \quad (9a)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{a}}^{n+1} = \bar{\mathbf{a}}^n + \frac{4}{h} \bar{\mathbf{v}}^n + \frac{4}{h^2} (\bar{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1} - \bar{\mathbf{u}}^n), \quad (9b)$$

where h is the time increment $h = t^{n+1} - t^n$.

Linearisation of the residual equations results in Eqs. (8a) and (8b) and gave the system of equations for iterative solution as stated in Eq. (10).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{4}{h^2} \mathbf{M}_u + \mathbf{K}_{uu}^{n+1} & \mathbf{K}_{up}^{n+1} \\ \mathbf{K}_{pu}^{n+1} & \mathbf{K}_{pp}^{n+1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{u}_{(i)}^{n+1} \\ \Delta \mathbf{p}_{(i)}^{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{u,(i)} \\ \mathbf{R}_{p,(i)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

With the spatial discretisation established, the hyperelastic–plastic governing equations were solved using an implicit, iterative Newton–Raphson scheme, as given in Appendix B. This scheme applied a radial return mapping to determine the material's plastic response, with the plastic hardening behaviour governed by Eq. (15), presented in Section 3.3. The reduction in load bearing capacity due to material damage was incorporated into the radial return step, where the effective damage parameter \bar{D} , defined in Eq. (11

contributed to stress reduction. Further details on damage and failure modelling are provided in Section 3.3.1. The radial return algorithm implemented within the PFEM scheme is outlined in Box 1

Box 1: Radial return algorithm

1. Set the initial values for the plastic strain tensor $\varepsilon_{p,n}$ and the left Cauchy-Green deformation tensor \mathbf{b}_n at the current time step n .
2. Define the trial function f_{n+1}^{trial} as:

$$f_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = \|\mathbf{s}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}\| - \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} (c_1 + c_2 \cdot \alpha_n + c_3 \cdot (1 - e^{c_4 \cdot \alpha_n})) (1 - \bar{D}_n), \quad (11)$$

where $\|\mathbf{s}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}\|$ is the norm of the trial deviatoric stress, c_1, c_2, c_3 , and c_4 are material parameters, α_n is the internal hardening variable, and \bar{D}_n is the damage parameter.

3. Elastic or Plastic Response:

If $f_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \leq 0$: The material response is elastic, and the algorithm exits.

Otherwise: Proceed with the Newton-Raphson iteration to solve the plasticity equations.

4. Perform iterative calculations until $R_{n+1} \leq \text{Tol}$ or $N_{\text{iter}} \geq N_{\text{max,iter}}$:

Define the consistency equations:

$$\bar{\mu} = \frac{\mu}{3} \text{tr}(\mathbf{b}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}), \quad (12a)$$

$$f' = 2\bar{\mu} + \frac{2}{3}(c_2 + c_3 \cdot c_4 e^{-c_4 \cdot \alpha_n})(1 - \bar{D}), \quad (12b)$$

$$\Delta^2 \gamma_{n+1} = \frac{f_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}}{f'}. \quad (12c)$$

Update the plastic multiplier and plastic strains:

$$\Delta \gamma_{n+1} = \Delta \gamma_n + \Delta^2 \gamma_{n+1}, \quad (13a)$$

$$\alpha_{n+1} = \alpha_n + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \Delta \gamma_{n+1}. \quad (13b)$$

Compute the residual R_{n+1} :

$$R_{n+1} = \|\mathbf{s}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}\| - 2\bar{\mu} \Delta \gamma_{n+1} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} (c_1 + c_2 \cdot \alpha_{n+1} + c_3 \cdot (1 - e^{c_4 \cdot \alpha_{n+1}})) (1 - \bar{D}). \quad (14)$$

5. If the residual R_{n+1} meets the tolerance, update the state variables and move to the next time integration step.

A more detailed description of the PFEM implementation, including further elaboration of the results variable transfer, discretisation and contact formulation is given by Sandin et al. [18].

3.3. Constitutive modelling

Accurate numerical representation of the blank deformation, up to high strain levels and until failure, was crucial as the blank endures extreme deformation during the shear cutting process. The plastic hardening response was therefore determined by hydraulic bulge testing according to the ISO 16808 standard [31], resulting in experimental data of effective stress versus plastic strain until material failure. The isotropic plasticity model proposed by El-magd et al. [32], shown in Eq. (15), was calibrated based on the bulge test data for describing the plastic hardening response in the numerical constitutive modelling. Table 4 states the plasticity model parameters c_1 to c_4 . As the CP1000HD material showed limited orthotropic response, the use of an isotropic plasticity model and axisymmetric modelling was considered adequate.

$$\bar{\sigma} = c_1 + c_2 \cdot \varepsilon_p + c_3 \cdot (1 - e^{-c_4 \cdot \varepsilon_p}) \quad (15)$$

Table 4
Plasticity model parameters c_1 to c_4 .

c_1 [MPa]	c_2 [MPa]	c_3 [MPa]	c_4
909.5	296.6	229.3	31.1

Table 5
Dimensionless MMC parameters C_1 to C_3 .

C_1	C_2	C_3
0.1103	1.7166	0.4003

3.3.1. Damage- and failure modelling

As most ductile metals, the CP1000HD grade experiences stress-state dependent failure behaviour and loss of the load-bearing capacity at high strain levels due to void growth and coalescence. This phenomenon was considered by an uncoupled local ductile damage- and failure model, based on the *Generalised Incremental Stress State Dependent Damage Model* (GISSMO), and was added to the isotropic plasticity model. GISSMO was proposed by Neukamm et al. [33] and further developed by Effelsberg et al. [34] and Andrade et al. [35,36]. The ductile damage- and failure model accumulates a damage parameter D according to the principle of Eq. (16), where $\varepsilon_f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$ is the stress-state dependent failure strain values further described in Section 3.3.2, $\dot{\varepsilon}_p$ is the plastic strain increment and n defines the damage accumulation rate. The stress-state parameters consists of the stress-triaxiality η and the normalised Lode angle parameter $\bar{\theta}$ which are commonly found in numerical implementations of damage and failure models, as they provide a consistent and intuitive representation of stress states.

$$\dot{D} = \frac{n}{\varepsilon_f(\eta, \bar{\theta})} D^{(1-\frac{1}{n})} \dot{\varepsilon}_p \quad (16)$$

Similarly, an instability parameter F accumulates according to Eq. (17), where $\varepsilon_{ins}(\eta)$ is the stress-state dependent instability strain, further elaborated in Section 3.3.2.

$$\dot{F} = \frac{n}{\varepsilon_{ins}(\eta)} F^{(1-\frac{1}{n})} \dot{\varepsilon}_p \quad (17)$$

The effective damage parameter \bar{D} is then defined by Eq. (18), where D_c is the value of the accumulated damage parameter D at the point of damage coupling, i.e. when $F = 1$. Here, m denotes the load bearing degradation rate of the stress tensor.

$$\bar{D} = \left(\frac{D - D_c}{1 - D_c} \right)^m \quad (18)$$

When the accumulated damage parameter D reaches a critical values of $D_{crit} = 0.99$, material failure is assumed and the element is removed from the post-preprocessing routine for visualisation purposes. This critical value is chosen to ensure a sufficient reduction in stiffness, such that the element no longer influences the solution.

3.3.2. Calibration of the damage- and failure model

Calibration of stress-state dependent failure strain values, $\varepsilon_f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$, was conducted by determining experimental failure strain values at plane stress according to the work by Marth et al. [37], using four tensile specimen designed to deform and fail at designated stress-states. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) measurements and utilisation of the Stepwise Modelling Method (SMM) by Marth et al. [37] enabled calibration of the modified Mohr-Coloumb (MMC) locus by Bai and Wierzbicki [38,39]. The MMC locus is given by Eq. (19), here reduced for von Mises plasticity, and the parameters C_1 , C_2 , C_3 were calibrated with least-squares curve fitting. Since plane stress was assumed, Eq. (20) was used for relating η to $\bar{\theta}$, thus obtaining a general 3D failure locus. Such representation is necessary knowing that the blank undergoes substantial deformation and failure in plane strain conditions [40]. Table 5 states the calibrated MMC parameters C_1 , C_2 , C_3 .

$$\varepsilon_f(\eta, \bar{\theta}) = \left\{ C_2 \left[\sqrt{\frac{1+C_1^2}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{\theta}\pi}{6}\right) + C_1 \left(\eta + \frac{1}{3} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{\theta}\pi}{6}\right) \right) \right] \right\}^{-\frac{1}{C_3}} \quad (19)$$

$$\bar{\theta} = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \cos^{-1} \left(-\frac{27}{2} \eta \left(\eta^2 - \frac{1}{3} \right) \right) \quad (20)$$

The instability strain values $\varepsilon_{ins}(\eta)$ utilised in Eq. (17) were obtained as the effective plastic strain values at peak force during the tensile testing. The tabulated instability strain values are presented in Table 6 with the corresponding stress triaxiality. Linear interpolation was used for values in between the tabulated points, with constant extrapolation for triaxialities outside the calibrated range.

The DIC measurements used for obtaining the failure strain values $\varepsilon_f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$ utilised a facet size of 100 μm . Consequently, the measured failure strain was directly correlated to a mesh size of comparable scale in the numerical model. For elements smaller than the reference size of 100 μm , mesh regularisation was employed to address the inherent mesh dependency associated with

Table 6
Effective plastic instability strain values $\epsilon_{ins}(\eta)$.

η	0.0	0.31	0.41	0.51
$\epsilon_{ins}(\eta)$	0.97	0.20	0.14	0.13

Table 7
Element size and the corresponding regularisation factor used for mesh regularisation of $\epsilon_f(\eta, \theta)$.

Element size [μm]	≥ 100	50	25	10	5
Reg. factor	1.0	1.1	1.15	1.30	1.40

Fig. 3. The initial PFEM discretisation for 12.1% cutting clearance, showing the symmetry axis and a magnified image of the SAZ mesh. The punch and die diameter is denoted D_p and D_d respectively. The tools are coloured dark grey, while the blank is light grey. The boundary conditions of the model are given with green (punch movement), red (fixed) and along the symmetry axis the radial movement was prohibited.

the local damage and failure model implemented in the PFEM scheme. The mesh regularisation technique, developed by Andrade et al. [36], adjusted the values of $\epsilon_f(\eta, \theta)$ by applying element size-dependent scaling factors. These scaling factors were determined through an iterative process, where fictitious notched tensile samples with progressively smaller characteristic element lengths were modelled. The scaling factors were calibrated to ensure that the force response of each sample matched that of a sample with the reference mesh size. In this way, mesh size dependency of the damage- and failure model was diminished. Table 7 states the elements sizes and their corresponding mesh regularisation factors. The range of element sizes ensured that all element sizes appearing in the PFEM modelling were adequately regularised.

3.4. Numerical modelling of sheet punching

The axisymmetric numerical sheet punching models consisted of tools and blank, as presented in Fig. 3. The tools were assigned a small strain elastic material model, while the blank was assigned the mixed formulation with the isotropic elastic–plastic model and the damage- and failure model presented in Section 3.3. The axial position of the die part was varied to change the cutting clearance when modelling each of the cases of Table 2. In Fig. 3, the green line states the punch tool boundary with the prescribed punch motion, while the red lines gives the fixed boundaries. The tool and blank boundaries along the symmetry axis were constrained in radial movement.

During the PFEM sheet punching simulation, the parameter h_{min} defines the minimum element size allowed by the re-connectivity scheme. In this work a minimum element size of $h_{min} = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$ was defined, giving a sufficiently fine SAZ discretisation at a reasonable computational time. Elements larger than $10 \mu\text{m}$ were incompatible with the sharp tool edge geometries, resulting in penetration in the tool edge contact. Meanwhile, elements smaller than $8.5 \mu\text{m}$ required more CPU-time, while producing cut edge morphologies similar to when using $h_{min} = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$. The initial discretisation close to the tool edges was defined to match h_{min} , as highlighted in Fig. 3. Both geometrical and mechanical criteria were used for defining the areas of particle insertion or re-connectivity. These criteria are in detail described by Sandin et al. [18].

3.4.1. Material rotation in the numerical model

Since the numerical blank was modelled as a homogeneous continuum, grains and thus grain rotations were not defined. Instead, the rotation of the material in the numerical model was compared to the grain rotations obtained experimentally. The numerical

Fig. 4. Experimental (a) and numerical (b) cut edge cross sections for 12.1% cutting clearance and corresponding paths for material rotation extraction.

material rotation was determined from the rotation tensor, \mathbf{R} , obtained through polar decomposition of the deformation gradient, \mathbf{F} . This procedure was described by Bonet et al. [30], by first determining the Cauchy–Green tensor \mathbf{C} as stated in Eq. (21) using the deformation gradient for each increment.

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{U}^2 \quad (21)$$

The eigenvalues of \mathbf{C} , λ_i^2 and eigenvectors \mathbf{N}_i were used to define the stretch tensor, \mathbf{U} , as in Eq. (22), where $i = 1, 2, 3$ denotes the principal directions of the axisymmetric coordinate system.

$$\mathbf{U} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \lambda_i \mathbf{N}_i \otimes \mathbf{N}_i \quad (22)$$

With \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{U} , the rotation tensor \mathbf{R} was calculated according to Eq. (23).

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{U}^{-1} \quad (23)$$

Now, the elemental angle increment around the out-of-plane axis was calculated using the four-quadrant inverse tangent between $\mathbf{R}_{2,1}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{1,1}$. By adding each elemental incremental angle change for each time step, the total material rotation angle θ was determined for each element.

The material grain rotation was experimentally measured for six vertical positions along the cut edge and into the SAZ width (*Burnish start*, *Burnish centre*, *Burnish end*, *Fracture start*, *Fracture centre* and *Fracture end*). This generated two-dimensional paths into the SAZ width where the grain rotation was extracted with even steps. Correspondingly, from numerical modelling the calculated material rotation at the same positions as in experiments. Fig. 4 shows the paths for the 12% cutting clearance case and the points of grain rotation measurement in (a) and the corresponding numerical paths and material rotation calculations points.

4. Results and discussion

By comparing the numerical- and experimental cut edge morphology, the accuracy of the damage- and failure model was investigated since the distribution of cut edge parameters to most extent is controlled by the fracture process. A comparison between experimental- and numerically obtained cut edge morphologies was done by overlaying the experimental- and numerical cut edge profiles. Experimentally, these were determined by 3D optical profile method presented in Section 2. The experimental results were extracted at positions 0° , 90° , 180° and 270° to the rolling direction around the punched hole circumference. From numerical modelling, a single cut edge profile was obtained for each cutting clearance due to the axisymmetric assumption. The overlaid experimental- and numerical cut edges are shown in Fig. 5. By overlaying the experimental- and numerical cut edge profiles, the numerical cut edges were easily compared to experimental results.

The final cut edge results were also defined in terms of the characteristic cut edge parameters, i.e. rollover height, burnish height, fracture height and burr and their respective distribution over the blank thickness. The experimental results were obtained for the entire range of cutting clearances presented in Table 2 using the 2D optical EISYS method described in Section 2. These results are shown in Fig. 6, describing the average cut edge parameters as the black crosses and the circumferential variations as error bars. The numerical results are also plotted in Fig. 6, where clear correlation with the average experimental results was observed.

Fig. 5. Experimental cut edge profiles (colours) and axisymmetrical numerically predicted cut edges (black) overlaid. The experimental cut edge profiles were determined at 0°, 90°, 180° and 270° around the punched hole circumference. For 27.0%, additional cut edge profiles were extracted for providing information at no-burr and burr sections.

Fig. 6. The experimental- (black cross) and numerical (blue box) cut edge parameter results over the entire range of cutting clearances. Each graph shows the distribution of the cut edge parameter (rollover, burnish, fracture, burr) over the blank thickness, while the last graph states the burnish-to-fracture ratio.

The results in Figs. 5 and 6 show that with increasing clearance, a steady rollover growth was seen along with a moderate burnish reduction and strong fracture height decrease. Additionally, burr height rose with increasing clearance. The minimum value for burnish and burnish-to-fracture ratio was found around 15%–20% clearance for the CP1000HD material. This conforms with similar AHSS grades and is suggested to give optimum forming sheared edge forming properties [24].

Similarly, the comparison between experimental- and numerical fracture angles is displayed in Fig. 7. The fracture angles, denoted β , were measured from the experimental and numerical cut edge profiles in Fig. 5 following the definition of the fracture angle β in Fig. 2. Since the experimental cut edge cross sections were taken at different positions around the hole perimeter, the

Fig. 7. Comparison between experimental fracture angles determined at 0°, 90°, 180° and 270° around the punched hole circumference and the numerically determined fracture angle (blue) from axisymmetric sheet punching simulations. The fracture angles β was determined according to the definition in Fig. 2.

corresponding fracture angle measurements capture the variations associated with these position. Due to a slight non-coaxiality of the tools, marginal clearance deviation occurred which caused variations of cut edge morphology and consequently, the fracture angles. Here, both experimental- and numerical results showed an increase in fracture angle until burr appeared at 27.0% cutting clearance, which caused the fracture angle to decrease. At higher clearances $\geq 27\%$, it can be assumed that the burr width increases in some extent at the expense of fracture angle. For 27.0% cutting clearance, partial burr formation occurred which caused one part of the hole to have burr, while the other was without. Therefore, the no-burr/burr fracture angles are displayed in Fig. 7.

The numerical modelling managed to predict the appearance of burr between 23.8% and 27.0% cutting clearance, which appeared as a large geometrical notch at the bottom of the cut edge. The slight non-coaxiality of the tools caused a partial burr formation to materialise at 27.0% cutting clearance as this caused slightly varying cutting clearance in around the punched hole. The partial burr formation was not possible to detect in axisymmetric sheet punch modelling and the numerical results consequently represents the expected cut edge morphology for the intended cutting clearance. A similar effect of the slight non-coaxiality was found in the opposite side of the cutting clearance spectra, at 5.3%. Here the experimental cut edge results showed circumferential heterogeneity and formation of secondary burnish islands, as displayed in Fig. 8. Fig. 9 then shows the various shapes the experimental cut edge profiles obtained along the hole perimeter. In Fig. 9, experimental cut edge profiles are shown where in (a) a long burnish zone was obtained, in (b) where secondary burnish was detected and (c) shows cut edge sections with fairly low burnish-to-fracture ratio.

The secondary burnish phenomenon appears when the fracture angles from punch and die mismatch and do not meet in the primary fracture process. This phenomenon was detected in the numerical modelling as well, and the mismatching fracture angles are highlighted in Fig. 9(d). Unfortunately, the implicit PFEM formulation could not converge under the complex loads and fracture process involved with the secondary burnish, thus the entire 5.3% cutting clearance process could not be modelled. However, by predicting the mismatching fracture angles which was the root cause of the secondary burnish formation, enough information was extracted from the PFEM modelling to consider the formation to be predicted. The comparison between experimental and numerical results, expressed through both cut edge profiles and the distribution of characteristic cut edge parameters, clearly demonstrates that the PFEM shear cutting model is robust across a wide range of cutting clearances. It accurately reproduced diverse sheared edge surfaces with varying fracture mechanisms, including the formation of secondary burnish, and effectively predicted the cutting clearance critical for burr formation.

Comparing the numerical- and experimental punching process forces enabled additional validation of the PFEM punching model. From this investigation, it was apparent that varying the cutting clearance also had an effect on the process forces, as shown for the numerical force versus punch displacement results in Fig. 10. Here it was observed that punch displacement levels increased with

Fig. 8. For cutting clearance of 5.3%, secondary burnish formation (blank surfaces, separated from the top primary burnish) was observed in experiments around the cut edge circumference.

Fig. 9. For 5.3% cutting clearance, the experimental cut edge cross section are shown in coloured lines with (a) large burnish heights, (b) secondary burnish and (c) low burnish-to-fracture ratio and compared to black numerical cut edge profile. (d) shows the mismatching fracture angles as orange arrows from punch and die and the secondary burnish surface caused by the fracture angle mismatch.

greater clearance due to additional bending, while process forces decreased with larger clearance. Fig. 11 shows the experimental- and numerical peak forces for each cutting clearance, ranging from 5.3% to 40.3%, where the decline of peak force is obvious up until 33.7% cutting clearance where a saturation plateau of the peak force was detected.

The numerically predicted peak forces were 4%–7% lower than the experimental results. Possible reasons behind this are the assumption of the somehow arbitrary numerical friction coefficient of 0.1 for both punch- and die sheet contact and the perfect coaxial setup in the numerical model compared to the slight non-coaxiality of the experimental setups. These assumptions might not conform with real process properties and affected the contact force response of the model. The numerical punching energy (Fig. 11, right axis), defined as the area under the force–displacement curve through trapezoidal integration, shows that the higher punch intrusion associated with larger clearances significantly increases the punching energy. Formation of the large rolover and long burnish zone both interacts in the increased amount of energy needed for the punching compared to optimum cutting clearances around 10%–17%.

The interrupted punching experiments presented in Section 2.1 were performed in order to give detailed knowledge of the punching process. By investigating the cut edge morphology at different stages along the punching process, it was observed when and where the fracture process was initiated. Comparing the experimental results with the numerical modelling also enabled further validation of the damage- and failure model. Fig. 12 shows the experimental- and numerical force response for the 9.0% clearance punching, where the markers state the point of experimental interruption. The initial part of the experimental force versus punch displacement results was corrected with regard to the elastic machine compliance since this was neglected in the numerical modelling. Comparing the experimental- and numerical force versus displacement results shows that the numerical modelling can reproduce the experimental force levels for this particular machine with good accuracy with the above stated assumptions of friction coefficient after the compliance correction. The accurate prediction of punch displacement and force levels at failure indicates a well-calibrated failure model.

Experimental crack initiation, marking the initiation of the fracture process and the subsequent formation of the fracture surface, occurred between the interruption points *Int. 1* and *Int. 2*. This is displayed by the SEM images from *Int. 2*, shown in Fig. 13(a),

Fig. 10. Numerical force versus punch displacement results from processes with cutting clearances ranging from 5.3% to 40.3%.

Fig. 11. Experimental- and numerical peak forces ranging the cutting clearances from 5.3% to 40.3% and the corresponding numerical punching energy.

which reveal the first visible crack emerging from the die side. In Fig. 13, the experimental SEM images at *Int. 2* are shown for each sheet orientation, along with an image from the numerical modelling at the identical punch displacement level. In the simulation, the damage and failure model excluded elements near the die edge from post-processing, indicating material failure and the onset of the fracture process. This demonstrates that the numerical model accurately predicted material failure in the vicinity of the die edge, closely aligning with the observations from the experimental results. At this point, no cracks were initiated from the punch edge neither in experiment nor in simulation, as shown in Fig. 13(b). These results clearly state the accuracy of the numerical damage- and failure model implementation. Furthermore, the accurate prediction of fracture initiation near the die edge suggests that the results transfer scheme employed by Rodríguez et al. [19] effectively preserved the numerical variables. This approach prevented noticeable diffusion or smoothing across the multiple particle re-connectivities leading up to fracture.

The validation of the numerical modelling concerning cut edge morphology and process forces showed first and foremost the accuracy of the damage- and failure modelling and results preservation associated with the PFEM modelling. However, the damage imposed to the blank bulk material was also investigated by the experimental grain rotation measurements presented in Section 2 and numerically by the polar decomposition procedure in Section 3.4.1. By investigating the material orientation of the SAZ, it was possible to determine the SAZ width and level of deformation in the bulk material in this zone. Fig. 14 shows the experimental grain rotation results and the numerical material rotation output for the 12.1% cutting clearance edges. The figure consists of separate graphs for each rotation calculation path, from *Burnish start* to *Fracture end*, along with linear fitting of two lines corresponding to the shear localisation and rollover bending. The numerical modelling was overall able to predict the experimental grain rotation

Fig. 12. The experimental- and numerical force versus punch displacement results from full experimental punching and the four interrupted punching experiments presented in Table 3. The markers state the punch displacement levels at the corresponding punch interruption.

(a) SEM images at 0° and 90° to the rolling direction (RD), along with the numerical modelling results at the die edge at the corresponding punch depth.

(b) SEM images at 0° and 90° to the rolling direction (RD), along with the numerical modelling results at the punch edge at the corresponding punch depth.

Fig. 13. Images of the (a) die and (b) punch edges from interrupted punching experiments at interruption point *Int.2* and from the corresponding punch displacement in numerical modelling for 9.0% cutting clearance.

Fig. 14. Numerical and experimental grain rotation results for 12.1% cutting clearance.

along the SAZ paths with slight deviation in magnitude from the experimental results, especially for the 27.0% cutting clearance case found in Fig. C.20. However, the width of the total SAZ was accurately predicted by the numerical modelling. The reason behind the slight inaccuracy in rotation level appearing approximately at the distances $100 < x < 500 \mu\text{m}$ from the cut edge was due to limitations of the plasticity model. Using a plasticity model with enhanced shear deformation capabilities or using experimental calibration data for higher strain levels could possibly improve the material rotation correlation. The additional grain rotation results are presented in Figs. C.18 to C.20.

The overall correlation between numerical modelling and experiments was studied by including all grain-/material rotation results for each clearance. These results are presented in Fig. 15 for 12% cutting clearance and Figs. C.21 to C.23 for clearances 5%, 20% and 27%, showing an overall good correlation between the numerical modelling and experiments. In the figures, the horizontal distances from the cut edge were normalised with the blank thickness, thus the localised shear- and bending SAZ widths and curve intersection points were expressed as dimensionless parameters related to the deformation behaviour of the material. The SAZ intersection point, corresponding to localised shear deformation, seemed to be independent of clearance level at around 0.1 of the normalised edge distance ($150 \mu\text{m}$). The total SAZ on the other hand was much larger, between 0.3 and 0.5 of the normalised edge distance ($450\text{--}750 \mu\text{m}$) and was directly dependent on rollover bending. The splitting between shear and bending dominated contributions demonstrate the high strain localisation tendency of the CP1000HD grade. From a modelling perspective it is important to accurately capture the localised deformation near the cut edge, as this SAZ damage affect subsequent processes such as forming, fatigue or hydrogen embrittlement.

The results presented in Figs. 14 and 15 indicate that the blank material experiences substantial deformations in the burnish zone, with grain rotations nearing 90° near the cut edge. This observation suggests that the material can withstand significant compressive stresses without fracturing. As discussed by Zhao et al. [11], these compressive stresses likely inhibit the growth of material voids, preventing ductile failure during the shearing phase. Analysis of the stress triaxiality during the shear stage of the punching process reveals that the rollover and shearing phases subject areas close to the tool edges to high compressive stresses (see Figs. 16 (a) and 17 (a) for 12% and 33% cutting clearance, respectively). Upon fracture initiation, significant tensile stresses were observed, particularly in the 33% cutting clearance case (see Figs. 16 (b) and 17 (b)). The latter illustrates the origin of the substantial burr formation associated with large cutting clearance, where tearing tensile stresses acted across the shearing zone while compressive stresses prevented fracture at the die tool edge. The work by Sandin et al. [18] show that the deformation in the SAZ occurs at $\hat{\theta} = 0$, i.e. at plane strain. Therefore, generating a general 3D failure locus to acquire such failure strain data was deemed relevant, but a 2D locus for $\epsilon_f(\eta, 0)$ would have been sufficient.

5. Conclusions

This work shows the robustness of the PFEM approach to address sheet metal shearing processes. The modelling scheme has been validated in many different cutting conditions through comparison with experimental results. According to the results from extensive validation campaign and the detailed discussions the following conclusions can be drawn:

Fig. 15. Combined grain/material results for 12.1% cutting clearance.

Fig. 16. Triaxiality evolution during (a) shearing and (b) fracture initiation for 12% cutting clearance.

- The inherent re-discretisation properties of PFEM, combined with the ductile damage and failure model, make it possible to model phenomenological fracture with high accuracy over a large range of cutting clearances and for several types of final cut edge morphologies. The model predicts the cut edge morphology regardless of the fracture process involved during sheet shearing, showing the presence of secondary burnish at low cutting clearance and predicting the clearance where burr appears. The model also captures accurately the location and load where the first crack nucleates, while providing high-resolution predictions of the SAZ deformation. These aspects play a significant role in influencing the material’s performance in subsequent applications and highlight the relevance of the PFEM modelling approach in predicting favourable cutting conditions.
- After undergoing the extensive validation presented in this article, it is concluded that the PFEM shear cutting model can significantly contribute to broader research fields. Apart from conventional close cut sheet punching, these fields may include two-step shear cutting processes, virtual testing of new tool designs or tool materials, the effect of tool wear, the impact of open/close cutting on fatigue properties or hydrogen embrittlement susceptibility.
- A successful case of applying non-conventional numerical methods for common solid mechanical process is presented. By this, the authors of this article intend to widen the understanding of how to address large deformation solid mechanics problems.
- The axisymmetric formulation allowed for computationally affordable simulations. This is required for fast iteration loops in material development or process design. However, to gain deeper insights into challenges associated with the shear cutting process, expanding this study to three-dimensional modelling is recommended. This approach would be especially beneficial for addressing non-coaxiality, which contributes to circumferential variations in cut edge morphology, and for detecting edge

Fig. 17. Triaxiality evolution during (a) shearing and (b) fracture initiation for 33% cutting clearance, where burr was formed.

cracking that may occur during subsequent cold forming operations.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Olle Sandin: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Patrick Larour:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Juan Manuel Rodríguez:** Supervision, Software, Methodology. **Sergi Parareda:** Investigation. **Samuel Hammarberg:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jörgen Kajberg:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Daniel Casellas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process.

During the preparation of this work the author used ChatGPT4o in order to improve readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Patrick Larour reports a relationship with voestalpine Stahl GmbH that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Spatial discretisation

The finite element matrices and vectors in Eqs. (8a) and (8b) are computed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{P}_u(\mathbf{u}) &= \int_v \mathbf{B}_u^T \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \, dv, \\
\mathbf{f}_{u,\text{ext}} &= \int_v \mathbf{N}_u^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \, dv + \int_a \mathbf{N}_u^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \, da, \\
\mathbf{M}_u &= \int_v \rho \mathbf{N}_u^T \mathbf{N}_u \, dv, \\
\mathbf{M}_p &= \int_v \frac{1}{\kappa} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} \frac{dv}{J}, \\
\mathbf{F}_{p,\text{vol}}(\bar{\mathbf{u}}) &= \int_v \mathbf{N}^T \left(\frac{\ln(J)}{J} \right) \frac{dv}{J}, \\
\mathbf{f}_{p,\text{stab}}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) &= \int_v \frac{\alpha}{G} \bar{\mathbf{p}} (\mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} - \tilde{\mathbf{N}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{N}}) \frac{dv}{J}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

Here, \mathbf{B}_u is the deformation matrix for axisymmetric elements, $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ is the Voigt representation of the Cauchy stress tensor, and J is the Jacobian of the deformation gradient. The axisymmetric volume is defined as $dv = 2\pi x dA$, where x is the radial position of the element midpoint.

The stiffness components in the system of equations in Eq. (10) are defined as:

$$\mathbf{K}_{uu} = \mathbf{K}^{\text{geo}} + \mathbf{K}^{\text{mat}}, \tag{A.2a}$$

where

$$\mathbf{K}^{\text{mat}} = \int_v \mathbf{G}^T \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \mathbf{G} \, dv, \tag{A.2b}$$

$$\mathbf{K}^{\text{geo}} = \int_v \frac{1}{J} \mathbf{B}_u^T \hat{\mathbf{c}}^{\text{ep,mix}} \mathbf{B}_u \, dv. \tag{A.2c}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{up} = \int_v \mathbf{B}_u^T \mathbf{m} \mathbf{N} \, dv, \tag{A.2d}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{pu} = \int_v \frac{(1 - \ln(J))}{J^2} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{m}^T \mathbf{B}_u \, dv, \tag{A.2e}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{pp} = \int_v \frac{1}{J\kappa} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} \, dv. \tag{A.2f}$$

Here, \mathbf{m} is the second-order identity tensor, $\hat{\mathbf{c}}^{\text{ep,mix}}$ is the hyperelasto-plastic tangent compliance tensor, and J is the Jacobian determinant, further described by Sandin et al. [18].

Appendix B. Global time integration scheme

1. Set the initial values for the following variables:

$$\mathbf{u}_{n+1} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{p}_{n+1} = \mathbf{p}_n, \quad \mathbf{x}_{n+1} = \mathbf{x}_n, \quad \bar{\mathbf{b}}_{n+1}^e = \bar{\mathbf{b}}_n^e, \quad \varepsilon_{p,n+1} = \varepsilon_{p,n}.$$

Here, \mathbf{u} represents the nodal displacement vector, \mathbf{p} is the pressure vector, \mathbf{x} denotes the nodal coordinates, $\bar{\mathbf{b}}^e$ is the volume-preserving part of the elastic left Cauchy–Green tensor, and ε_p is the equivalent plastic strain.

2. Determine the displacements, pressure increments, and contact forces between the blank and tool by iterating over $i = 1, \dots, N_{\text{max,iter}}$, where $N_{\text{max,iter}}$ is the maximum number of iterations.
3. Update nodal displacements, pressures, and coordinates using the following equations:

$$\mathbf{u}_{n+1,(i+1)} = \mathbf{u}_{n+1,(i)} + \gamma \Delta \mathbf{u}_{n+1,(i)}, \tag{B.1a}$$

$$\mathbf{p}_{n+1,(i+1)} = \mathbf{p}_{n+1,(i)} + \gamma \Delta \mathbf{p}_{n+1,(i)}, \tag{B.1b}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{n+1,(i+1)} = \mathbf{x}_{n+1,(i)} + \gamma \Delta \mathbf{x}_{n+1,(i)}. \tag{B.1c}$$

Here, γ is a line search parameter, defining the magnitude of the increment step in direction of the displacement vector, and $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{p}$ represent incremental changes in displacement and pressure, respectively.

4. Calculate the relative deformation gradient $\mathbf{F} = \frac{d\mathbf{x}_n}{d\mathbf{x}_{n+1}}$, the Jacobian determinant J , and the element areas A_e for the updated configuration.
5. Compute the Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, the updated volume-preserving elastic left Cauchy–Green tensor $\bar{\mathbf{b}}^e$, and the equivalent plastic strain ε_p using the radial return mapping algorithm (described in Box 1).

6. Calculate the displacement residual \mathbf{R}_u and pressure residual \mathbf{R}_p , then verify convergence using the following conditions:

$$\|\mathbf{u}_{n+1,(i+1)} - \mathbf{u}_{n+1,(i)}\| \leq \text{TOL}_u \|\mathbf{u}_n\|, \tag{B.2a}$$

$$\|\mathbf{p}_{n+1,(i+1)} - \mathbf{p}_{n+1,(i)}\| \leq \text{TOL}_p \|\mathbf{p}_n\|, \tag{B.2b}$$

$$\|\mathbf{R}_{u,(i)}\| \leq \text{TOL}_u \max(\|\mathbf{P}_{u,n+1}\|, \|\mathbf{F}_{n+1}^{\text{ext}}\|), \tag{B.2c}$$

$$\|\mathbf{R}_{p,(i)}\| \leq \text{TOL}_p \max(\|\mathbf{F}_{p,\text{vol},n+1}\|, \|\mathbf{F}_{n+1}^{\text{stab}}\|). \tag{B.2d}$$

Here, TOL_u and TOL_p are convergence tolerances for displacement and pressure, $\mathbf{P}_{u,n+1}$ is the internal force vector, $\mathbf{F}_{n+1}^{\text{ext}}$ is the external force vector, $\mathbf{F}_{p,\text{vol},n+1}$ represents volumetric forces, and $\mathbf{F}_{n+1}^{\text{stab}}$ denotes stabilisation forces.

7. If the convergence criteria above are satisfied, the solution is considered converged. Otherwise, increment i and repeat the iteration.
8. For the updated configuration, calculate the damage parameter D as described in Section 3.3.1.

Appendix C. Grain rotation results

All experimental grain rotation results and numerical material rotation results plotted together for the cutting clearances 5.3%, 12.1%, 20.5% and 27.0%. Linear regression fitted lines for the shear localisation and rollover deformation is also shown, along with dashed lines stating the intersection points of the lines.

Fig. C.18. Numerical and experimental grain rotation results for 5.3% cutting clearance.

Fig. C.19. Numerical and experimental grain rotation results for 20.5% cutting clearance.

Fig. C.20. Numerical and experimental grain rotation results for 27.0% cutting clearance.

Fig. C.21. Combined grain/material results for 5.3% cutting clearance.

Fig. C.22. Combined grain/material results for 20.5% cutting clearance.

Fig. C.23. Combined grain/material results for 27.0% cutting clearance.

Data availability

The experimental datasets presented in this article are not readily available due to industrial confidentiality. The numerical data will be made available on request.

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